

1 **Hygroscopic Cycle for Enhanced Water Efficiency in Thermal Power Plants**

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43 **ABSTRACT**

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45 This article presents a methodology for calculating the potential for water savings
46 when replacing the Rankine cycle with the hygroscopic cycle in power plants. The savings
47 were analyzed in thermal power plants with different generating units (diesel, gas, steam,
48 combined cycle), different cooling systems (seawater open cycle, adiabatic cooling,
49 cooling tower), and in different climatic zones. The results indicated a maximum average
50 saving of 1.83 m³/MWh. The considerable water savings serve to reinforce the case for
51 the implementation of HCT, particularly in regions characterized by arid climates and
52 water scarcity. A reduction in water consumption, coupled with the prevention of the
53 return of hot water to sensitive ecosystems, can serve as effective mitigation strategies
54 for environmental problems. Moreover, the minimal water consumption required for this
55 process makes it feasible to construct thermal power plants and generate electricity in
56 regions with limited water resources. The HCT approach facilitates the generation of
57 energy in regions previously deemed unsuitable for thermal power plants, thereby
58 representing a significant advancement in economic and developmental terms for these
59 areas.

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61 **STATEMENT OF INDUSTRIAL RELEVANCE**

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63 The article is of particular interest to all industries that produce electricity and
64 employ traditional power cycles. The findings presented herein will provide these
65 industries with data on the environmental benefits of substituting traditional cycles with
66 the novel hygroscopic cycle in terms of cooling water consumption.

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68 **NOVELTY OR SIGNIFICANCE**

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70 The manuscript's distinctive contribution is to illustrate the savings in water
71 consumption that can be achieved when traditional power cycles are replaced by
72 hygroscopic cycles in power plants. Additionally, the manuscript presents a method for
73 calculating these savings.

74

75 **KEYWORDS**

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77 Water Consumption; Cooling Water; HCT; Power Cycles; Energy Efficiency

78

79 **NOMENCLATURE**

80

<i>AC</i>	adiabatic cooling
<i>BC</i>	Brayton cycle
<i>C</i>	combined cycle
<i>CT</i>	cooling tower
c_w	specific heat of water at constant pressure (J/kg)
<i>D</i>	diesel
<i>G</i>	gas
<i>GC</i>	Goswami cycle
HCT	hygroscopic cycle technology
<i>H</i>	equivalent hours (h)

h_{out}	enthalpy of water at the outlet of the cooling system (kJ/kg)
h_{in}	enthalpy of water at the inlet of the cooling system (kJ/kg)
KC	Kalina cycle
OP	open-cycle seawater
ORC	organic Rankine cycle
$O\&M$	operation and maintenance
RC	Rankine cycle
RCT	Rankine cycle technology
S	steam
T_{in}	temperature of water at the inlet of the cooling system ($^{\circ}C$)
T_{out}	temperature of water at the outlet of the cooling system ($^{\circ}C$)
\dot{m}	cooling water mass flow (kg/s)
\dot{m}_w	mass flow rate for the cooling process (kg/s)
\dot{m}_{m-u}	make-up water mas flow rate (kg/s)
\dot{Q}_C	power released by the cooling system (kW)
\dot{Q}_F	heat rejected by thermal cycle of the plant (kW)
\dot{V}_w	volume flow rate of water consumed (m^3/s)
\dot{W}	net power plant (kW)
V_w	volume of water consumed (m^3)

β_t	addition of percentages of the cooling mass flow rate
η	power plant efficiency
ρ_w	water density (kg/m ³)
τ	number of hours that the plant is operation per year (h/year)

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82

83 **INTRODUCTION**

84

85 In recent years, interest in the use of renewable energy sources as a source of
86 electricity has increased significantly. The climate policies [1,2] agreed upon by the major
87 energy producing and consuming countries, as well as the rising prices of these raw
88 materials, are the driving forces. However, power generation from these "clean" sources
89 cannot yet replace traditional power generation from fossil fuels such as coal or gas.
90 Moreover, the use of these traditional energy sources in developing countries has
91 increased significantly in recent years. According to the World Energy Outlook 2022 [3],
92 the world's energy supply from clean sources has reached 38%, but there is an
93 unprecedented increase in the level of pollutant emissions associated with electricity
94 generation, and electricity generation from coal. Therefore, the need to improve the
95 efficiency of processes and minimize the environmental impact of electricity generation
96 from non-renewable sources is extremely important.

97 The research presented in this article goes in this direction, which is to improve
98 the thermal cycle used in thermal power plants fired with hydrocarbons or coal. The
99 Rankine Cycle (RC) used in these plants uses steam, and although it is a mature
100 technology, its effectiveness is still improving due to its wide and widespread use in
101 various industrial processes over time. Due to its widespread application, the efficiency
102 gains achieved using RC have a significant global impact in improving energy production
103 processes and reducing associated pollutant emissions, as well as increasing the economic
104 viability or financial capability of power plants that use it [4]. Figure 1 [5] shows the
105 scheme of RC used in a thermoelectric plant.

106 To enhance the efficacy of this cycle [6-8], recent studies have concentrated on
107 reducing the irreversibility and associated losses by proposing advanced supercritical
108 steam cycles [9, 10], regenerative generation [11, 12], overheating and binary. Moreover,
109 efforts are made to maintain steam quality at or above 90% at the steam turbine outlet,
110 and to prevent steam from entering the process pump. Other lines of research
111 concentrate on enhancing efficiency by substituting the clean water utilized in the cycle
112 with alternative fluids introduced into the turbine. This has resulted in the development
113 of the Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) [13], which has an almost identical configuration to
114 that of the conventional RC but is designed for low-energy thermal work and
115 temperatures between 80 and 400°C. ORC [14-17] employs the use of pure organic fluids,
116 which may encompass a range of refrigerants and organic compounds.

117 The utilization of a "dry" fluid obviates the necessity for superheating the steam
118 [18], as is the case with Rankine Cycle Technology (RCT), which markedly reduces the
119 operating temperature and evaporating pressure while enhancing the efficiency of the
120 cycle. Isothermal mixtures or liquids with different boiling points are also employed in
121 ORC, albeit to a lesser extent. A comparative analysis of the performance of a cycle
122 utilizing isothermal mixtures or dry liquids, as evidenced by studies [19, 20], indicates that
123 enhancements in process performance are only achievable under highly specific
124 operational conditions. One such instance is when water is cooled to a constant
125 temperature. Nevertheless, its utilization may prove advantageous considering the
126 mounting environmental concerns. An intriguing example of a zeotropic mixture is the
127 combination of water and ammonia utilized in the Kalina Cycle (KC). The Kalina Cycle (KC)

128 permits greater flexibility in the composition of the mixture, although its configuration is
129 more intricate. Nevertheless, it represents a significant alternative [21] to pure ORC,
130 offering a notable reduction in heat source consumption and enhanced efficiency,
131 partially attributable to its diminished degree of irreversibility [22]. In contrast [23-25],
132 other studies have identified additional constraints, including process optimization, the
133 choice of working fluid, and the type of heat source.

134 Improvements have also been studied using a genetic algorithm in the Brayton
135 cycle (BC) of supercritical CO₂ for waste heat recovery from simple cycle gas turbines
136 using [9]. Other cycles [26] that use energy from low-medium heat sources are the
137 Goswami cycle (GC), which uses a binary mixture. They also consist of a combination of
138 liquid water and ammonia with RC and an adsorption cycle [27]. Other studies [28],
139 performed with different zeotropic mixtures and RC operating conditions, have allowed
140 improvements in ORC characteristics of up to 15%. In addition [29], it should be
141 remembered that environmental conditions significantly influence the lifetime of
142 different types of thermodynamic cycles. From this perspective, water scarcity, both in
143 the energy generation process and in the cooling process at the end of the cycle,
144 combined with high ambient temperatures, can hinder the use of the thermodynamic
145 process. Rising temperatures and water shortages are becoming increasingly serious due
146 to climate change. For this reason [30], power generation must use as little water as
147 possible, as 10% of the world's available water is used in power generation, mainly in the
148 cooling stage. Therefore, the so-called hygroscopic cycle technology (HCT) [7] appears as
149 an improvement of the traditional thermoelectric generation cycle, improving the

150 thermal efficiency of the cycle, reducing the water consumption for cooling, and allowing
151 thermal cycling in areas where high ambient temperatures would make electricity
152 generation difficult or impossible.

153 Figure 2 [5] illustrates the configuration of HCT, which is founded upon the RC
154 principle but incorporates enhancements within the cooling zone to capitalize on
155 physicochemical absorption processes. In HCT [5], hygroscopic compounds are employed
156 as part of the working fluid to augment steam condensation at the turbine outlet due to
157 the absorption process. The hygroscopic substances [31] utilized in HCT must satisfy
158 specific criteria. They must be non-flammable, exhibit a vapor pressure that is lower than
159 that of pure water, and therefore exhibit reduced volatility compared to water.
160 Additionally, they must possess the ability to attract surrounding water vapor and be
161 readily separable to facilitate subsequent vapor desorption (reversible retention).

162 In addition, the substances in question must be non-toxic and chemically stable
163 under the conditions typically encountered during HCT operations. The LiBr-H₂O mixture
164 proposed in reference [32] is an appropriate working fluid for HCT. The soluble and
165 hygroscopic nature of this salt enables its utilization throughout the entirety of the HCT
166 cycle, thereby facilitating the attainment of optimal results. The solubility of LiBr [33] is
167 markedly enhanced with rising dissolution temperature. Concurrently, the separation of
168 water vapor and hygroscopic compounds does not necessitate the utilization of
169 specialized desorption technology or supplementary heat sources. The HCT [34] has been
170 successfully implemented in operational facilities with a generating capacity ranging from
171 12.5 MW to 50 MW.

172 Global warming is expected to influence power cycles, causing different
173 technologies to adapt to increasingly higher cooling temperatures, both for air and water.
174 RC, BC, and C are currently the most widely used in thermal power plants around the
175 world. However, the necessary environmental adaptations place HCT with a great
176 capacity for development and implementation. However, due to the recent
177 advancements in this field, there is a paucity of comparative studies between HCT and
178 other cycles. Nonetheless, research conducted in 2023 [34] substantiates that the exergy
179 efficiency of HCT is 2.2 % higher than that of regenerative RC, and its thermal efficiency is
180 2.26 % higher. This study also validates the reduced water consumption of HCT and
181 underscores its preeminent role in shaping the future of the energy sector.

182 In the HCT, the process of steam condensation by absorption occurs within the
183 absorber, where the clean exhaust from the turbine (state 2 in Figure 2) is mixed with an
184 aqueous solution of hygroscopic compounds in a low concentration (state 3 in Figure 2).
185 The enhancements attained through the process of condensation by absorption [35] are
186 as follows:

- 187 • Due to the lower condensing pressure required at each cooling temperature,
188 the electrical output of the turbine increases compared to the RC, thus
189 increasing the overall electrical efficiency of the cycle.
- 190 • At a given condensing pressure, the condensing temperature increases and
191 thus the cooling temperature increases. Therefore [34], the heat dissipation
192 of the condensed energy can only be achieved by air and therefore does not
193 require water. By not using traditional water-cooling processes in cooling

194 towers, you can avoid water consumption and save on cooling tower
195 maintenance costs.

- 196 • At the same time, by eliminating the need for cooling water, thermoelectric
197 processes can be used to generate energy in areas where water is scarce.
- 198 • Reduced energy demand [34] of cooling systems consisting of dry coolers since
199 the increase in condensing temperature requires less dissipated thermal
200 energy.

201 With all these features, HCT can improve traditional RC and increase electrical
202 efficiency by about 2.5%, save up to 50% on demineralized water and additive
203 consumption, reduce investment costs by 5%, and reduce operation and maintenance
204 (O&M) costs by 25%, increasing the availability of the technology and its longevity [6].
205 The features and improvements achieved by HCT technology are of particular interest for
206 use in areas with warm climates.

207 This study presents a novel methodology for simulating the implementation of
208 HCT in thermal power plants, with the objective of calculating the potential cooling-water
209 savings that can be achieved by replacing traditional cycles with HCT. To validate the
210 methodology, the results are compared with those of real power plants located in
211 different parts of the world. The methodology offers a valuable means of assessing the
212 prospective cooling water savings in power plants facing water scarcity through the
213 implementation of HCT, while simultaneously enhancing the plant's efficiency and
214 availability.

215

216 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

217

218 The methodology used to calculate water savings by implementing HCT in
219 thermoelectric plants is based on the specific characteristics and cooling system of each
220 thermal power plant. With HCT, dry coolers are used for cooling and the need for water
221 consumption is eliminated. As a result, significant savings in cooling water consumption
222 can be achieved. In addition, HCT targets areas where thermoelectric cycles are
223 impractical due to water scarcity.

224 The climates considered for the validation of the methodology were the Atlantic,
225 Mediterranean-Atlantic, Mediterranean, Oceanic, Subtropical, Semi-arid and Desert.
226 They plants are in Spain, Italy, Chile, and Argentina. Gas, diesel, steam turbine and
227 combined cycle power plants were analyzed. The cooling systems were adiabatic cooling,
228 open-cycle seawater, and cooling tower. In addition, a detailed list of thermoelectric
229 power plants by climate, country, group type, and cooling system with the number of
230 units and their power capacity can be found in Table 1.

231 For each power plant, the thermal power released by the cooling system (\dot{Q}_C) can
232 be calculated by equation (1). Being \dot{W} the net power plant and η the power plant
233 efficiency.

234
$$\eta = \frac{\dot{W}}{\dot{Q}_C + \dot{W}} \quad \Longleftrightarrow \quad \dot{Q}_C = \dot{W} \cdot \left(\frac{1-\eta}{\eta}\right) \quad (1)$$

235 The relationship between the necessary water mass flow rate (\dot{m}_w) for the cooling
236 process and the thermal power released by the cycle is given by equation (2). Being h_{in}
237 and h_{out} the enthalpies of water at the inlet and outlet of the cooling system,
238 respectively.

239
$$\dot{Q}_C = \dot{m}_w \cdot (h_{in} - h_{out}) \quad (2)$$

240 Considering the specific heat capacity of water (c_w), the cooling mass flow rate
 241 can be calculated as in equation (3). Being T_{in} and T_{out} the temperatures of water at the
 242 inlet and outlet of the cooling system, respectively.

243
$$\dot{m}_w = \frac{\dot{Q}_C}{c_w \cdot (T_{in} - T_{out})} \quad (3)$$

244 Denoting the temperature change as ΔT , equation (3) can be rewritten as
 245 equation (4).

246
$$\dot{m}_w = \frac{\dot{Q}_C}{c_w \cdot \Delta T} \quad (4)$$

247 Consequently, the mass flow rate of water can be obtained by equation (5).

248
$$\dot{m}_w = \frac{\dot{W} \cdot \left(\frac{1-\eta}{\eta}\right)}{c_w \cdot \Delta T} \quad (5)$$

249 The make-up water mass flow rate (\dot{m}_{m-u}) that is necessary to add in the cooling
 250 cycle to compensate for the water losses and to accomplish the mass conservation of the
 251 cooling system depends on the cooling technology of the plant. In general, it is mainly due
 252 to purges (for avoiding scale and incrustations), evaporation and dragging of water
 253 droplets. Each of them can be obtained as a percentage of the cooling mass flow rate. If
 254 β_t is the addition of those percentages, the necessary mass flow can be calculated
 255 according to equation (6).

256
$$\dot{m}_{m-u} = \beta_t \cdot \frac{\dot{W} \cdot \left(\frac{1-\eta}{\eta}\right)}{c_w \cdot \Delta T} \quad (6)$$

257 The volume flow rate of water consumed (\dot{V}_w) can be calculated by equation (7),
 258 where ρ_w is the water density.

259
$$\dot{V}_w = \frac{\beta_t}{\rho_w} \cdot \frac{\dot{W} \cdot \left(\frac{1-\eta}{\eta}\right)}{c_w \cdot \Delta T} \quad (7)$$

260 Considering the number of hours that the plant is operation per year (τ), the
 261 annual water consumption of the plant (V_w) can be obtained by equation (8).

262
$$V_w = \tau \cdot \frac{\beta_t}{\rho_w} \cdot \frac{\dot{W} \cdot \left(\frac{1-\eta}{\eta}\right)}{c_w \cdot \Delta T} \quad (8)$$

263 The data regarding the refrigeration system and the power of the various units
264 were obtained from two sources: the state register of emissions and polluting sources
265 and the environmental declaration of each power plant [36-48]. Consequently, the data
266 utilized in this study are derived from technical documents of the electricity companies
267 that possess the plants and official documents issued by public institutions in the various
268 areas examined.

269 Accordingly, the groups using steam performed 33%, using petrol 38%, using
270 diesel 45%, and using combined cycle 60% [49-52]. The values considered of parameter
271 β_t for the different cooling systems were 0.1% for the adiabatic cooling, 0.51% for the
272 open-cycle seawater, and 2.4% for the cooling tower [53-55]. For ΔT a value of 14 °C has
273 been taken according to the common industrial values [6].

274 It was also necessary to know the equivalent operating hours. These hours were
275 calculated from the annual production data for each type of plant, which are available in
276 the Canary Islands energy yearbook 2021 [56], the power plant information + EU registry
277 and the State registry of emissions and polluting sources provided by the Government of
278 Spain [57-63], the Storage Technique of Power Plants of South America [43] and the
279 Technical Reports of Italian Power Plants [64-66]. A total of 35 actual power plants were
280 used for the validation of the methodology. These data are presented in Table 1. The
281 columns in Table 1 show the following.

282 Power Plant: The name or title of the power plant.

283 Group Type: The definition of the plant type and its working cycle is imperative.
284 The following acronyms are used to describe the different power plant types: C for
285 Combined cycle, D for Diesel, G for Gas, and S for Steam. Consequently, combined cycle
286 power plants employ the Brayton+Rankine cycle; diesel power plants utilize the Diesel
287 cycle; gas (turbine) power plants employ the Brayton cycle; and steam power plants use
288 the Rankine cycle.

289 Cooling System: The cooling systems employed in these power plants are classified
290 as follows: adiabatic cooling (AC), cooling tower (CT), and open-cycle seawater (OP). An
291 adiabatic cooling system constitutes a hybrid cooling method that integrates components
292 of both air and evaporative cooling. Cooling towers constitute a component of a closed-
293 loop cooling system, wherein water circulates between the power plant and the cooling
294 tower, thereby releasing heat into the atmosphere through the process of evaporation.
295 An open-cycle seawater cooling system involves the extraction of substantial quantities
296 of seawater from proximate oceans or substantial bodies of water for the purpose of
297 cooling the plant's condenser. The absorbed heat is subsequently discharged back into
298 the source, often at an elevated temperature.

299 Units: A power plant unit is defined as a self-contained power generation system,
300 comprising turbines, generators, boilers (if applicable), cooling systems, and supporting
301 infrastructure. The quantity of each power plant unit is indicated in this column.

302 Power capacity: is defined as the maximum electrical output that a power plant
303 can produce under ideal operating conditions.

304 Equivalent hours: refer to the total number of hours a power plant would need to
305 operate at full capacity to generate the same amount of energy it produced over a given
306 period. The calculation involves dividing the total energy produced (in MWh) by the
307 power capacity (in MW).

308 Table 2 presents the climate conditions, geographical location, and annual water
309 requirements for each power plant.

310
311 **RESULTS**

312
313 The methodology has been validated with the actual data of the 35 power plants
314 presented in Table 1. The annual water consumption of the plants was calculated
315 according to equation (8) and the values have been included in column 5 of Table 2. The
316 actual data of annual consumption of the power plants [43, 57-66] have been compared
317 to those obtained by means of the methodology and the deviations are lower than 4.5%
318 in all cases. Consequently, the methodology can be used for the estimation of the
319 potential water savings with an acceptable margin of error.

320 Figure 3 shows the cooling water consumption vs. the efficiency of the cycle used
321 in the power plant for the different cooling systems. The results indicate that when
322 increasing the efficiency of the cycle, the water consumption decreases. Also, the higher
323 consumption is for cooling towers with a greater rate of decrease (from 4.5 m³/MWh for
324 efficiencies of 25% to 0.5 m³/MWh for efficiencies of 75%). The decrease of water
325 consumption for the Open-Cycle is moderate (from 0.9 to 0.05 m³/MWh for the range of
326 efficiencies considered). Finally, the consumption in the case of the adiabatic cooling is

327 very small compared with the other system, ranging from 0.35 to 0.01 m³/MWh for the
328 range studied. Consequently, the potential of consumption can be quantified for the
329 different cycles and cooling systems, and the plants with cooling towers have the
330 maximum potential of water savings when the HCT is implemented instead of the classic
331 cycles.

332 Figure 4 shows the average water savings (m³/MWh) that can be obtained for the
333 different cooling systems calculated with the data presented in the paper. The systems
334 with cooling towers can avoid 1.83 m³ of water MWh produced if the HCT is implemented.
335 For a power plant with cooling system based on cooling towers, functioning 7000 h per
336 year, the potential water savings with HCT would be 640500 m³/year. For the Open-Cycle
337 seawater, the average value is 0.57 m³/MWh, about 31% of the consumption with cooling
338 towers. In that case, for a power plant with the conditions of the previous example, the
339 potential savings would be of 199500 m³/year. Finally, if the power plant uses the
340 adiabatic cooling, the savings are much lower, 0.06 m³/MWh (about 3.3% of the
341 consumption with cooling towers). In the case of the example, for adiabatic cooling, the
342 saving would be 21000 m³/year.

343 Figure 5 displays the average water savings for different types of plants (Diesel,
344 Gas, Steam and Combined Cycle). They were obtained with the data presented in the
345 paper. Greater savings can be obtained when the Steam cycle is replaced by HCT (0.64
346 m³/MWh). Savings with Diesel and Combined Cycle are similar, with 0.39 and 0.34
347 m³/MWh respectively. The lower value corresponds to plants of Gas with a value of 0.1
348 m³/MWh. The savings with Steam plants are about double than those of Diesel and

349 Combined cycles, and the saving of Gas plants are about 15.6% of those with Steam
350 Cycles. For the example of a power plant of 50 MW functioning 7000 h/year, the savings
351 would be 224000, 136500, 119000 and 3500 m³/year for Steam, Diesel, Combined Cycles,
352 and Gas Cycles, respectively.

353

354 **DISCUSSION**

355 The implementation of the HCT system is particularly recommended in areas
356 experiencing water shortages. The technology in question precludes the consumption of
357 cooling water. The greatest savings are achieved in power plants with cooling towers. In
358 power plants with open-cycle seawater cooling, the savings are 31.15% of those achieved
359 in power plants with cooling towers. In power plants that use cooling systems, these
360 savings are 3.30% compared to those that use cooling towers.

361 The savings in water used for cooling are illustrated in Figure 4, which
362 demonstrates the environmental significance of employing HCT cycles in comparison to
363 other conventional thermodynamic cycles utilized in power plants. Furthermore, due to
364 the minimal water consumption necessitated, it is feasible to construct power plants and
365 generate electricity in regions with scarce water resources, enabling the generation of
366 energy in areas that were previously unsuitable for thermoelectric plants. The capacity to
367 construct power plants in arid regions, where water availability has historically been a
368 constraining factor, engenders novel prospects for energy generation. This expansion of
369 potential plant locations can reduce infrastructure costs related to water transportation
370 and supply, contributing to lower overall project expenditures. Furthermore, the

371 development of energy production in regions experiencing water scarcity has the
372 potential to attract investments, stimulate local economies, and generate employment
373 opportunities by enabling industrial expansion that was previously constrained by water
374 limitations.

375

376 **CONCLUSION**

377 A validated methodology has been developed to calculate the water savings when
378 replacing traditional thermal power generation technologies and cooling systems with
379 HCT. It allows us to estimate the potential savings based on the efficiency of the cycle and
380 the cooling system. The maximum savings can be obtained when Steam cycles are
381 replaced by the Hygroscopic cycle (1.83 m³/MWh on average). Regarding the cooling
382 system, replacement of cooling towers allows the maximum water savings (0.64 m³/MWh
383 on average).

384 The results indicate that the amounts of water that can be saved are considerable,
385 and this fact also confirms the interest in installing the HCT, especially in regions with arid
386 climates and water scarcity. By avoiding water consumption for industrial processes and
387 preventing the return of heated water to sensitive ecosystems, as in open cooling
388 systems, environmental issues can be alleviated.

389 The implementation of HCT has been demonstrated to offer substantial water
390 savings, while concurrently enhancing economic viability through a reduction in operating
391 expenses, an extension of plant sitting options, and an assurance of compliance with
392 environmental regulations. The long-term financial advantages, when considered in

393 conjunction with the environmental benefits, position HCT as a strategic investment for
394 sustainable power generation in regions experiencing water scarcity.

395

396 **CREDIT AUTHORSHIP CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT**

397

398 **Juan Carlos Ríos-Fernández:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis,
399 Investigation, Methodology, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing- original draft
400 and editing. **Víctor Manuel Fernández-Pacheco:** Data curation, Investigation, Resources.

401 **Alessia Manfredi:** Conceptualization, Software, Visualization. **Francisco Javier Rubio-**
402 **Serrano:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Resources. **Antonio J. Gutiérrez-Trashorras:**
403 Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Writing-review & editing.

404

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418

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Figure Captions List

- Fig. 1 Diagram of a thermoelectric power plant with Rankine Cycle
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- Fig. 5 Water savings potential with HCT for different group types of power plants

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Table Caption List

Table 1	Characteristics of the thermoelectric plants
Table 2	Annual water consumption for cooling system in thermoelectric plants

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Fig. 1. Operation diagram of a thermoelectric power plant utilizing the Rankine cycle

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Fig. 2. Operation diagram of a thermoelectric power plant utilizing the Hygroscopic

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cycle

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663 **Fig. 3.** The relationship between water consumption and cycle efficiency across various

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cooling systems

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Fig. 4. Potential water savings in power plants using HCT for different cooling systems

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Fig. 5. Potential water savings using HCT across different power plant categories

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Table 1. Characteristics of the thermoelectric plants

Climate	Country	City/Island	Power Plant	Group Type	Cooling System	Units	Power Capacity (MW)	Equivalent hours (h)		
		Fuerteventura	Las Salinas	D	OP	9	107.92	4421.5		
			Las Salinas	G	AC	3	79.1	399		
		Gran Canaria	Jinámar	D	OP	5	84	3824.9		
			Jinámar	G	AC	3	98.45			
			Barranco Tirajana	G	AC	6	376			
			Jinámar	S	OP	2	120	1469.2		
			Barranco Tirajana	S	OP	4	320.73			
			La Gomera	El Palmar	D	OP	6	13.38	3.354.8	
		El Palmar		D	AC	3	7.79			
		La Palma	Los Guinchos	D	OP	10	82.84	2880.1		
			Los Guinchos	G	AC	1	22.5	22.2		
		Lanzarote	Punta Grande	D	OP	11	199.76	3167.5		
			Punta Grande	G	AC	2	62.5	201.3		
		Tenerife	Candelaria	D	OP	3	36	2107.5		
			Granadilla	D	OP	2	48			
			Candelaria	G	AC	3	92.2	3348.3		
			Granadilla	G	AC	6	382.9			
			Arona	G	AC	2	50			
			Isora	G	AC	1	44			
			Candelaria	S	OP	2	80	1513.7		
			Granadilla	S	OP	4	313.4			
		Cadiz	Arcos de la Frontera	C	CT	3	1600	1340.65		
			San Roque	C	CT	1	831	125.73		
		Huelva	Palos de la Frontera	C	CT	3	1188	1501.96		
		Mediterranean		Castellon	Castellon	C	OP	2	1612	1007.16
				Murcia	Escombreras	C	OP	3	1269	680.45
				Barcelona	Besos	C	OP	2	826	2436.39
			Italy	Aprilia	Aprilia	G	AC	2	545.4	2577
						S	AC	1	260.2	
				Modugno	Modugno	G	AC	2	551.3	1318
						S	AC	1	260.2	
		Mediterranean-Atlantic								
Atlantic										

		Termoli	Termoli	G	AC	2	532.6	1904
				S	AC	1	248.1	
Desert	Chile	Valparaiso	Ventanas	S	OP	3	747	5745.70
		Tocopilla	Tocopilla	S	OP	2	276	6155
		Antofagasta	Angamos	S	OP	2	558	6297
		Cochrane	Cochrane	S	OP	2	550	6662
Oceanic	Italy	Turano Lodigiano	Turano Lodigiano	G	AC	2	554.4	2268
				S	AC	1	264.8	
Semi-arid	Chile	Vallenar	Guacolda	S	OP	5	764	6577
	Argentina	Salta	Termoandes	S	CT	3	643	4576

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Table 2. Annual water consumption for cooling system in thermoelectric plants

Climate	Country	City/Island	Power Plant	Annual Water Consumption (m ³ /year)
		Fuerteventura	Las Salinas	182974.30
			Las Salinas	3167.78
		Gran Canaria	Jinámar	76387.26
			Jinámar	182144.81
			Barranco Tirajana	
			Jinámar	412460.87
		Barranco Tirajana		
		La Gomera	El Palmar	11474.93
			El Palmar	654.98
		La Palma	Los Guinchos	91488.434
			Los Guinchos	50.14
		Lanzarote	Punta Grande	242629.55
			Punta Grande	1262.79
		Tenerife	Candelaria	90619.85
			Granadilla	
			Candelaria	191257.83
			Granadilla	
			Arona	
			Isora	
			Candelaria	379317.95
Granadilla				
Mediterranean-Atlantic	Cadiz	Arcos de la Frontera	2111317.57	
		San Roque	102839.06	
Atlantic	Huelva	Palos de la Frontera	1756276.84	
Mediterranean	Castellon	Castellon	339578.83	
	Murcia	Escombreras	298165.47	
	Barcelona	Besos		

	Italy	Aprilia	Aprilia	85141.40
		Modugno	Modugno	86063.69
		Termoli	Termoli	60961.84
Desert	Chile	Valparaiso	Ventanas	11208133.70
		Tocopilla	Tocopilla	1082097.42
		Antofagasta	Angamos	2238190.84
		Cochrane	Cochrane	2333976.83
Oceanic	Italy	Turano Lodigiano	Turano Lodigiano	76197.36
Semi-arid	Chile	Vallenar	Guacolda	3200740.19
	Argentina	Salta	Termoandes	8819973.42

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